

Bernt Isak Wærstad

Ghost Doctor Duplicate

Performance

Video of presentation can be found [here](#)

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Bernt Isak Wærstad¹

¹ Norwegian Academy of Music, Oslo, Norway
bernt.i.waerstad@nmh.no

“Ghost Doctor Duplicate” is an improvised performance and also the name for an evolving digital music instrument system. Both the performance and the instrument system is part of an ongoing artistic research project at the Norwegian Academy of Music named “Instrument design using machine learning and artificial intelligence” (Wærstad 2020). The goal of this project is to explore and develop new digital instrument design strategies through techniques more idiomatic to the digital domain rather than attempting to copy behaviour or physical properties of acoustic instruments. By using both generative and adaptive techniques from machine learning, AI and computational creativity, this project aims to produce a fauna of adaptive and somewhat autonomous digital musical instruments. An artistic presentation of the project will be given with this solo performance for electric guitar and electronics, where the “Ghost Doctor Duplicate” system serve as an adaptive extension of the electric guitar based on my performance style and techniques.

Through my participation in “Cross adaptive processing as musical intervention”¹, I have worked with several MIR techniques for the purpose of doing adaptive processing. The approach we used in my collaboration with Gyrid Kaldestad and Bjørnar Habbestad, where to rather start with musical gestures than a specific analysis technique. Recording and feeding those musical gestures into a variety of analysis tools enabled us to pick the features which where best suited to identify and differentiate the various gestures. Building on my experience from that project, I have been exploring similar features for self-adaptive processing purposes. Instead of mapping the feature values directly to processing parameters like we did in the cross-adaptive project, I wanted to explore the effect of using machine learning to “pick out” the right analysis technique. For this performance, I’m using a system which feeds an array of analysis parameters (MFCC, spectral centroid, RMS, etc.) into a GMM algorithm. I picked out and recorded 10 different musical gestures (using a bow, picking strings hard, using a rubber mallet, etc.) which where fed in to the system. The 10 categories coming out of the GMM algorithm could then be mapped to a variety of effect parameters. Since the algorithm always produces 10 likelihood values for each of the categories, you can get a huge space of variations to explore whenever you play something which is even slightly different from the original recorded reference gestures. The goal was to have a more open-ended system which had more room to explore though probably with a downside of being less comprehensible. I was not too worried about this downside, as my experience from the cross adaptive project where that understanding the cause and effect relationship was mostly important during design and testing, but quickly became less important when we started playing as we reverted from analysing what was going on to intuitively responding to the sounds produced and applied processing.

One of the potential issues of a responsive instrument is that it is constantly responding (i.e., changing). As a mean of counter this, a simple switch to freeze the analysis by toggling the GMM algorithm on and off. This made it easier for me to take back control when needed and quickly became an interesting musical effect in it self as a way of working with repetition. I also included an expression pedal to control the averaging of the likeliness output from the GMM algorithm making it possible to go from snappy response to smooth and gradual transitions. Another interesting musical effect that came up during rehearsals, was combining looped material with live input in to the same analyser. Somewhat similar to the cross adaptive project where the sound from one musician would affect processing of the other musician(s), only here my previous sounds would affect my current sound and visa versa. For the future, I also plan to explore this sort of temporal interplay in parallell having two sets of analysers and audio processors.

Wærstad, B. I., 2020, “Instrument design using machine learning and artificial intelligence”, *Proceedings of the International Conference on Live Interfaces*, NTNU Trondheim

¹ <http://crossadaptive.hf.ntnu.no/>